

Supplementary Information

PG-DWA: A Pheromone-Guided Global Planning and Local Obstacle Avoidance Method for UAVs in Complex Urban 3D Environments

S1. Selection of the Best Traditional Algorithm

To identify the most advantageous conventional algorithm in terms of path length for subsequent comparison with the proposed method, a further evaluation is conducted among the three baseline planners. The three-dimensional flight trajectories generated by the three algorithms are presented in [Figure S1](#). All three planners successfully find feasible paths from the start point to the goal while avoiding static obstacles. The Traditional A* trajectory (blue solid line) follows a relatively direct route with sharp directional changes near obstacle boundaries. The Weight-Adaptive A* trajectory (purple dashed line) produces a marginally longer but geometrically smoother path by modulating heuristic weights in regions of varying obstacle density. The RRT* trajectory (green dashed line) exhibits characteristic spatial randomness inherent to sampling-based exploration, yet achieves a competitive path length owing to its asymptotic optimality property.

Figure S1. Three-dimensional flight trajectory comparison of baseline algorithms.

Quantitative performance metrics are summarized in [Table S1](#) and [Figure S1](#). The Traditional A* achieves a flight time of 66.40 s with a path length of 122.31 m and an average speed of 1.84 m/s, representing the best time efficiency among the three baselines. RRT* yields a comparable flight time of 66.60 s and the shortest path length of 121.43 m, while consuming the least energy (153.2 units), benefiting from its sampling-based geometric optimization. The Weight-Adaptive A* requires 70.60 s to complete a longer path of 127.80 m at a reduced average speed of 1.81 m/s, with the highest energy expenditure of 161.0 units; the increased cost is attributable to the adaptive weight mechanism introducing additional spatial detours for smoother turning behavior.

Table S1. Performance Comparison of Baseline Path-Planning Algorithms.

Algorithm	Flight Time(s)	Speed (m/s)	Path Length (m)
Traditional A*	66.40	1.84	122.31
Weight-Adaptive A*	70.60	1.81	127.80
RRT*	66.60	1.82	121.43

A critical observation from [Table S1](#) is that none of the three baseline algorithms triggers any path replanning event during the mission. As purely global planners, these methods compute a single trajectory at the mission outset and rely entirely on this pre-computed path for guidance throughout the flight. While this strategy suffices in quasi-static scenarios, it exposes a

fundamental limitation: when dynamic obstacles intrude upon the planned trajectory - as frequently occurs in real urban low-altitude environments - these planners lack the capacity for online trajectory reconstruction, rendering them susceptible to collision risks, prolonged hovering, or mission failure.

Moreover, the heuristic functions of all three algorithms are constructed exclusively from geometric quantities (Manhattan distance, Euclidean distance, altitude difference, or random spatial sampling), without any mechanism to encode, accumulate, or reuse historical flight experience. Even if a replanning mechanism were externally imposed, each replanning episode would restart the search from scratch, unable to exploit previously discovered safe corridors or persistently suppress known high-risk regions, resulting in redundant exploration and degraded replanning efficiency.

Based on the above analysis, the Traditional A* algorithm is selected as the global planning component for the subsequent evaluation, owing to its superior time efficiency and near-optimal path length. To compensate for the absence of local reactive control in global-only planners, it is coupled with the Dynamic Window Approach (DWA) to form an A*-DWA hybrid framework, which provides real-time local obstacle avoidance while maintaining global path coherence. This A*-DWA configuration serves as the direct comparison baseline for the proposed Pheromone-enhanced A* algorithm. As will be demonstrated in the following subsections, the purely geometric heuristic within this baseline framework leads to the characteristic “avoidance → wait → return to original path” behavior under dynamic obstacle interference, whereas the pheromone field mechanism proposed in this work enables proactive, experience-driven path reconstruction that substantially improves flight efficiency and environmental adaptability.

[S2. Performance Metrics and Statistical Reporting of Different Urban Scene Configurations](#)

This supplementary document presents extended simulation experiments conducted to assess the generalization capability and statistical robustness of the A*-DWA algorithm and the PG-DWA algorithm. Independently generated urban scene configurations were evaluated through 15 separate trials. In all cases, static obstacles are placed through a pseudo-random program that ensures the scene is physically navigable from the start to the end, and maintains the spatial density range observed in the low-altitude urban airspace targeted in the paper.

For each configuration and each algorithm, the following metrics are recorded per trial: total flight time, average flight speed, number of obstacle avoidance events, number of global path re-planning events, and total avoidance duration.

Figures S2 to S16 present the simulation outputs of PG-DWA across 15 independently generated map configurations. The left panels illustrate the initial obstacle layouts along with the start and goal positions, whereas the right panels depict the flight trajectories upon either successful mission completion or early termination. All 15 map configurations employed in this PG-DWA series satisfy the flight metrics, with the complete flight paths clearly visible. These results confirm the universality of PG-DWA across diverse map environments.

Figure S2. Randomly generated map configuration 1 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S3. Randomly generated map configuration 2 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S4. Randomly generated map configuration 3 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S5. Randomly generated map configuration 4 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S6. Randomly generated map configuration 5 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S7. Randomly generated map configuration 6 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S8. Randomly generated map configuration 7 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S9. Randomly generated map configuration 8 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S10. Randomly generated map configuration 9 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S11. Randomly generated map configuration 10 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S12. Randomly generated map configuration 11 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S13. Randomly generated map configuration 12 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S14. Randomly generated map configuration 13 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S15. Randomly generated map configuration 14 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S16. Randomly generated map configuration 15 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figures S17 to S31 show the A*-DWA simulation outputs for 15 independently generated map configurations. Each figure follows the same panel conventions as the PG-DWA series: the left panel shows the initial obstacle layout and start/goal positions, while the right panel shows the drone trajectory upon task completion or termination. These series are generated under the same procedural constraints and share the same algorithm parameters, obstacle density range, dynamic obstacle settings, and flight space dimensions, ensuring that cross-algorithm comparisons are methodologically valid. Figure S25 reports a task failure in this map configuration, where interaction with dynamic obstacles prevents the drone from returning to its original path, indicating that the A*-DWA reactive replanning strategy could not resolve the issue within the allotted task time.

Figure S17. Randomly generated map configuration 16 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S18. Randomly generated map configuration 17 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S19. Randomly generated map configuration 18 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S20. Randomly generated map configuration 19 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S21. Randomly generated map configuration 20 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S22. Randomly generated map configuration 21 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S23. Randomly generated map configuration 22 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S24. Randomly generated map configuration 23 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S25. Randomly generated map configuration 24 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S26. Randomly generated map configuration 25 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S27. Randomly generated map configuration 26 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S28. Randomly generated map configuration 27 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S29. Randomly generated map configuration 28 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S30. Randomly generated map configuration 29 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

Figure S31. Randomly generated map configuration 30 flight process, initial map, final flight state.

S3. Comparison of Performance Results

Tables S2 and S3 show the mean of total flight time, average speed, avoidance duration, and number of replans for the two algorithms after 15 trials each.

Pheromone Influence (%) reports the trial-averaged pheromone modulation factor as a percentage. This factor scales the DWA control gains at each timestep based on the local balance between the path attraction layer and the avoidance repulsion layer of the pheromone field. A value of 100% denotes a neutral condition in which the pheromone field exerts no net effect on control outputs. Values above 100% indicate that the path attraction layer is locally dominant, causing the pheromone field to augment control responsiveness along historically validated corridors. Values below 100% indicate elevated repulsion-layer concentration near obstacle or avoidance zones, where the pheromone field moderates control gains to reduce overcorrection risk. For the related formulas and explanations, please refer to Formula 3 in the original text.

The comparison results between [Table S2](#) and [Table S3](#) indicate that under identical scene generation rules, obstacle density, and dynamic interference conditions, PG-DWA exhibits a significant overall advantage over A*-DWA. The flight time of PG-DWA is generally shorter (most configurations range from 79 s to 168 s, while A*-DWA often exceeds 150 s, even reaching 300 s or resulting in mission failure), the average flight speed is higher (1.3~1.8 m/s vs. 0.6~1.2 m/s), and the path length does not increase significantly. More importantly, A*-DWA frequently falls into local optima in multiple configurations (up to 19 times) and experiences mission failures due to deadlocks ([Figure S25](#)), whereas PG-DWA successfully completes the mission in all 15 random scenarios, with more efficient obstacle avoidance behavior.

Table S2. Average values of key indicators for different PG-DWA configurations.

Configuration	Path Length (m)	Number of Obstacle Avoidances	Time (s)	Pheromone Influence	Speed (m/s)
1	126.7	3	109.2	94.5%	1.39
2	177.3	13	108	93.9%	1.88
3	121.1	10	83.2	102.1%	1.76
4	109.8	7	79	87.3%	1.71
5	161.9	10	145.8	104.1%	1.29
6	112.7	5	94.6	124.9%	1.46
7	142.3	8	167.8	97.7%	0.96
8	147.4	9	97.2	126.4%	1.78
9	125	7	91	87.9%	1.65
10	133.1	11	91.2	93.0%	1.74
11	178.8	11	144.6	95.2%	1.41
12	116.2	11	98.2	87.5%	1.44
13	107.5	1	85.8	96.1%	1.55
14	131	9	92.2	126.2%	1.70
15	145.7	8	111.6	99.1%	1.53

Table S3. Average values of key indicators for different A*-DWA configurations.

A*-DWA	Time (s)	Path Length (m)	Speed (m/s)	Number of Obstacle Avoidances	Number of local optima
1	158.4	181.4	1.15	3	5
2	155.2	146.39	0.94	8	2
3	237.4	223.78	0.94	5	7

4	300	194	0.65	12	19
5	176.8	183	1.03	18	7
6	300	276	0.92	14	9
7	239.6	168.77	0.7	12	4
8	204.6	205	1	4	7
9	300	275.53	0.91	69	8
10	182.4	189.85	1.04	7	6
11	132	167.3	1.26	4	5
12	154.6	164.62	1.06	10	5
13	168.2	174.57	1.03	6	4
14	264.8	279.75	1.06	9	6
15	134.2	143.49	1.07	4	3

Table S4 reports the average flight time and speed of the two algorithms under each configuration, as well as the standard deviation of flight time, to allow for direct comparison between different scenario types. The average flight time of PG-DWA is lower than that of A*-DWA, the average speed is higher than that of A*-DWA, and the standard deviation of flight time is smaller, indicating that PG-DWA has less performance fluctuation and greater stability across different urban scenarios. Therefore, at the macro level, it demonstrates that PG-DWA not only performs better under a single configuration but also has good generalization ability and statistical consistency.

Table S4. Mean values of key indicators for different configurations.

Algorithm	Flight time (s)	Average Length (m)	Average speed (m/s)	Number of replans	Avoidance Events
A*-DWA	207.21	185.2	0.98	2	12
PG-DWA	135.73	186	1.51	14	12